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**The Design of an Adaptive Learning System for Students with Learning
Disabilities in Nigerian Special Education Schools**

**A study submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree of MA,
Education Framework**

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ABSTRACT

This research explores the design of an adaptive learning system for students with learning disabilities in Nigerian special education schools, using a small number of private Nigerian special education schools in Lagos State, Nigeria, as a case study. Interviews were conducted online via Google Meet video in English to gather sufficient data on the Design of an Adaptive Learning System for Students with Learning Disabilities in Nigerian Special Education Schools. The investigator used purposeful sampling, choosing 10 teachers from different private Nigerian Special Education Schools who were chosen as the respondents. In addition, the study employs thematic analysis using the qualitative data collected from the participants. Thus, the findings of the study revealed two learning challenges faced by students with learning disabilities, namely cognitive/behavioural challenges and communication/social difficulties. According to the findings, the most fundamental tasks in learning, such as reading, spelling and arithmetic, are hampered by delays in processing and behavioural frustrations. The findings also highlighted that the lack of digital infrastructure, unreliable electricity and internet, poor learning environment, lack of government/policy support, and limited teacher training on technology hinders the implementation of adaptive learning systems.

Chapter One

1.0 Introduction

This chapter discussed the background study that examined the design of an adaptive learning system for students with learning disabilities in Nigerian special education schools. Additionally, my experience, which forms the basis of this investigation, was also discussed, highlighting the importance and the purpose of the study, while introducing what comes after in the next chapter.

1.1 Background of the Study

In the past few years, the education sector has come to understand the value of inclusivity and the necessity of meeting the diverse learning needs of students, particularly those with learning disabilities (Navas-Bonilla *et al.*, 2025). These disabilities include issues with language, writing, and mathematical expression, as well as occasionally being linked to slow learning or attention issues (Kristén, Klingvall and Ring, 2020). Integrating creative methods and flexible tactics into teacher education is crucial to preparing aspiring teachers to help every student fairly (McMahon and Walker, 2019). Even if this move is becoming more popular worldwide as a result of providing enough care and attention to individual students with learning disabilities, several regions globally, like Nigeria, confront particular difficulties in putting these changes into practice (Tondeur *et al.*, 2016). These difficulties are frequently linked to socioeconomic limitations, restricted access to learning materials, and the requirement for infrastructure that can successfully incorporate technology into the teaching and learning process (Tondeur *et al.*, 2016). Hence, education programs ought to have a specific skill set and access to relevant resources that foster an inclusive learning environment in order to offer the necessary support for students with learning difficulties.

Learning disabilities include a variety of cognitive challenges, including dyslexia, dyscalculia, dysgraphia, dysphonia, and others, that make it difficult for a student to study at the same rate as their classmates without specialised assistance (Sofologi *et al.*, 2022). To give educators the information and abilities they need to meet these particular requirements, teacher education programs are essential (van Geel, Keuning and Safar,

2022). However, in Nigeria, there is still little integration of technology-based solutions and specialist teaching methods into these programs (Adebimpe, 2025). Creating a supportive learning environment for all students requires creative solutions that combine inclusive teaching practices and contemporary technology tools in order to close this gap (Plooy, Casteleijn and Franzsen, 2024). The development of educational technology presents encouraging opportunities to improve teacher training, particularly in inclusive education (Navas-Bonilla *et al.*, 2025). Technology plays a key role in creating assistive gadgets, visual aids, and adaptive learning tools that can lessen learning difficulties (Shumilova, Prano and Makuha, 2022). In addition, teacher educators who succeed in their roles possess the technical know-how to use these tools and have an open and welcoming mindset (Smeins, Wildenburg and Duarte, 2022). As a result, conventional teaching techniques must give way to integrative approaches that promote diversity and assist students with learning disabilities.

Adaptive learning is a revolutionary approach to education, especially for students with exceptional needs, which involves customising educational experiences to meet the unique learning problems and styles of each student (Nazmi *et al.*, 2023). This method ensures that students receive individualised training that meets their unique needs by acknowledging the diversity of learners, especially those with special needs (Horna-Saldaña and Canaleta, 2024). It is impossible to overestimate the importance of adaptive learning for special needs in a time when inclusion is crucial (Damyanov, 2024). Adaptive learning is important because it increases student engagement and educational effectiveness, allowing students with learning disabilities to advance at their own speed by gaining access to specialised tools that address a range of learning challenges (Mariappan *et al.*, 2023). This approach improves overall educational outcomes by creating an inclusive environment where all students can succeed (Mariappan *et al.*, 2023). Students are encouraged to take charge of their education through self-directed learning, which is another benefit of adaptive learning for special needs (Kruger, 2021). Real-time assessments and feedback loops allow teachers to quickly modify learning courses, which improves retention and motivation (Haleem *et al.*, 2022), making it suitable for students who might find it difficult in conventional learning environments. Hence, by

using adaptive learning techniques and creating an equitable learning environment that successfully serves various learners, students with disabilities can eventually achieve their full potential, and achievement gaps can be closed.

Several essential components of adaptive learning systems provide customised learning experiences, especially for those with learning disabilities (Kolluru, Mungara and Chintakunta, 2018). These systems tailor information using data-driven algorithms, making sure that learning paths are tailored to the individual needs of every learner (Kolluru, Mungara and Chintakunta, 2018). An essential component of adaptive learning is real-time assessment, which regularly assesses students' development and modifies the curriculum according to their areas of strength and weakness (Plooy, Casteleijn and Franzsen, 2024). This makes it possible for teachers to change lesson plans and step in quickly to maximise learning results (Plooy, Casteleijn and Franzsen, 2024). Another important aspect is the incorporation of multimedia elements into the teaching methods (Abdulrahaman *et al.*, 2020). According to Abdulrahaman *et al.* (2020), adaptive learning systems integrate films, interactive simulations, and gamified components that accommodate a variety of learning styles and promote students' engagement and retention. Moreover, it's critical to have flexibility in instructors' learning rate as students could advance at their own pace, which enables them to grasp ideas before moving on (Mishra, 2024). Therefore, these components are beneficial in special education adaptive learning since they foster self-assurance and sustained academic achievement.

Adaptive learning offers a host of benefits that are tailored to meet the various needs of students with learning disabilities. Adapting instructional materials to each student's skills, paces, and learning styles improves engagement and creates a positive learning atmosphere (Nazmi *et al.*, 2023). Students are able to advance at their own pace, which lessens frustration and fosters a feeling of accomplishment (Nazmi *et al.*, 2023). Instant feedback from adaptive learning systems allows for prompt modifications to learning pathways to better suit the needs of each learner (Contrino *et al.*, 2024). Additionally, using data analytics to monitor development is another benefit as teachers effectively keep an eye on each student's progress, which enables them to make well-informed judgments about additional training or interventions (Tong, Uyen and Ngan, 2022). Better

learning results are promoted by this capacity, which guarantees that every student receives sufficient help (Tong, Uyen and Ngan, 2022). Furthermore, by making education accessible, adaptable learning promotes diversity, allowing all students to participate more easily because of the availability of tools and resources made for different learning profiles (Goyibova *et al.*, 2025). Thus, the use of data-driven support, real-time feedback, and personalised instruction can help improve the engagement of students with learning difficulties.

However, the successful implementation of adaptive learning for students with learning disabilities may be hampered by a number of issues. Accessibility concerns are prevalent since many adaptive learning systems might not be made to meet the demands of people with different learning styles (Dagunduro *et al.*, 2024). This could lead to inequalities and exclusion of students who need these technologies (Dagunduro *et al.*, 2024). In addition, many educational institutions lack the resources and capital needed to create or use adaptive technologies for students with special needs (Fteiha *et al.*, 2024). Due to their frequently limited funding, special education schools in Nigeria lack access to necessary resources for adaptive learning (Oredein and Obadimeji, 2022). The situation is further complicated by technological obstacles, as some teachers lack the necessary abilities to use adaptive learning aids successfully, which makes valuable technologies underutilised (Johnson *et al.*, 2016). Hence, barriers to accessibility, a lack of finance, and insufficient teacher preparation all impede the effective adoption of adaptive learning in Nigerian special education schools.

In my experience as an instructor in one of the Nigerian special education schools for students with learning disabilities, I have seen the usefulness of adaptive learning systems in helping students with special needs to learn better. I made use of an adaptive learning platform like multimedia to create classes specifically tailored to the needs of students with autism. The outcomes demonstrated significant gains in academic performance and engagement, highlighting the beneficial effects of the approach. In addition, I noticed that students with dyslexia were helped by making use of a specialised adaptive learning program. These students were able to read at grade level in less than a year because the program provided individualised reading materials and interactive

exercises. However, challenges of a lack of funding and the effective use of adaptive learning systems limit the reach of this endeavour. As a result, adaptive learning systems improve learning outcomes of students with learning disabilities irrespective of the challenges that they bring.

The increased awareness of inclusive education around the world and the pressing need to modify teaching strategies for Nigerian students with learning difficulties serve as justifications for this study (Lynch, Singal and Francis, 2022). Although there is proof that adaptive learning systems can enhance student engagement, comprehension, and overall academic performance, Nigerian special education schools confront particular obstacles to their successful implementation, including a lack of funding, a lack of teacher preparation, and technological limitations (Lynch, Singal and Francis, 2022). By examining how adaptive learning technologies could be successfully developed and implemented to support inclusive individualised education in under-resourced special education contexts, this research aims to close the gap caused by Nigeria's current educational practices, which frequently fall short of meeting the diverse needs of students with disabilities. Hence, the next chapter will review the currently existing themes, while offering in-depth discussions which is backed by scholarly research for the themes. Theories and empirical evidence will also be analysed in the next chapter concerning the topic at hand.

Chapter Two

Literature Review

2.0 Introduction

This chapter focuses on reviewing existing literature to resolve the underlying issue of this study, which is to explore the design of an adaptive learning system for students with learning disabilities in Nigerian Special Education Schools. In addition, this chapter will also discuss the themes of this study, which entail the adaptive learning system, adaptive learning system and learning disabilities in special education schools, adaptive learning system and individual needs of students with learning disabilities, key learning challenges faced by students with learning disabilities and technological and infrastructural barriers in implementing adaptive learning systems in special education schools. In addition, the following questions (what are the key learning challenges faced by students with learning disabilities in Nigerian special education schools?; what technological and infrastructural barriers exist in implementing adaptive learning systems in Nigerian special education schools?; how can an adaptive learning system be tailored to meet the individual needs of students with various types of learning disabilities?) would guide this chapter. Furthermore, this chapter will discuss theories and empirical studies relevant to the study and conclude by identifying gaps in the literature.

2.1 Adaptive Learning Systems

The advancement of technology has presented the opportunity to create customised teaching, which allows students to choose their learning paths, thus leading to the emergence of personalised learning (Contrino *et al.*, 2024). In brief, personalised learning is an educational technique in which the objectives, learning speed, content sequence, and instruction can vary according to the needs of the students; one of the ways of approaching this technique is Adaptive Learning (Kolluru, Mungara and Chintakunta, 2018; Contrino *et al.*, 2024).

Adaptive learning systems or technologies have emerged as one of the most significant innovations in contemporary education, offering a personalised, technology-driven

approach to instruction that adjusts in real-time to the unique needs, abilities, and performance of each learner (Wambui, 2024). Thus, personalised adaptive learning systems are built based on the fact that the learning process differs for each learner (Essa, Celik and Human-Hendricks, 2022). This is quite different from the current systems (or static or traditional digital tools), which offer the same content or resources to all students irrespective of their individual learning needs or preferences (Essa, Celik and Human-Hendricks, 2022).

While adaptive learning systems are dynamic, they use artificial intelligence and data-driven algorithms to dynamically modify the pace, content, and delivery of instruction in response to student performance and engagement (Gligorea *et al.*, 2023). These systems are appealing because they can close the long-standing gap between learner diversity and standardised curricula, which is especially problematic when it comes to the education of students with learning disabilities (Alkhaldeh, Ahmad and Khasawneh, 2021).

In addition, the adaptive learning systems consist of three (3) basic elements, viz: the content model, learner model, and teaching model (Alkhaldeh, Ahmad and Khasawneh, 2021). The content model defines the conceptual structure or selects the appropriate content based on what the student knows or the level he has reached; while the learner model captures the student's existing knowledge base, learning pace, and concludes the student's learning style; and lastly, the teaching model (which entails the information from the content and learner model) defines how to choose a specific content, for a particular student at a specific time (Alkhaldeh, Ahmad and Khasawneh, 2021). Through this interplay, the adaptive learning system creates a feedback loop that is individualised, responsive, and constantly evolving.

2.2 Adaptive Learning Systems and Learning Disabilities in Special Education Schools

Every student learns and acquires knowledge in a unique way (Alkhaldeh, Ahmad and Khasawneh, 2021). Alkhaldeh, Ahmad and Khasawneh (2021) classified learners into verbal, visual, auditory, kinesthetic, sequential, reflective, quantitative and qualitative

learners. Thus, when designing and preparing electronic content, the learning environments had to consider these patterns based on these classifications (Alkhaldeh, Ahmad and Khasawneh, 2021). By their design, the adaptive learning system ensures a responsive and dynamic approach to instruction, which is specifically beneficial to students with disabilities who often require personalised or customised instruction (Asian Development Bank, 2022).

The term “Learning Disabilities”, is often referred to as “hidden/invisible disabilities” because they are not readily noticeable, unlike physical disabilities, entail a variety of neurodevelopmental conditions that impair a student’s ability to effectively learn, comprehend and communicate information (Dreyer, 2021). Attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD), auditory and visual processing disorders, dyslexia (difficulty with reading), dyscalculia (difficulty with math), and dysgraphia (difficulty with writing) are a few examples of learning disabilities (Kemp, Smith and Segal, 2018; Walden University, 2023). According to Nigeria’s Federal Ministry of Budget and Planning and UNICEF (2024), about 6-8% of school-aged children in Nigeria, between the ages of 7-14 years, may be living with one or more forms of learning disabilities.

The adaptive learning systems address one of the challenges faced in special education schools, which has to do with the heterogeneity of the learners' needs (Balami, Oparaugo and Dimshaka, 2023). Students in the same class may vary widely in cognitive ability, pace of comprehension, learning style and emotional regulation (Balami, Oparaugo and Dimshaka, 2023). However, the traditional instructional methods are poorly suited to accommodate such diversity because they only linearly deliver a uniform curriculum (Essa, Celik and Human-Hendricks, 2022).

Hence, the effectiveness of adaptive learning in special education cannot be overemphasised. The use of adaptive learning software in special needs schools can help improve literacy outcomes, especially for children with dyslexia and aid students with ADHD exhibit greater focus and content retention (Al-Dokhny, Bukhamseen and Drwish, 2022; Vincent, Okeowo and Ariyo, 2024; Thawalampola *et al.*, 2024).

However, it is worth noting that the introduction of adaptive learning systems is not a solution to the educational challenges faced by learners with disabilities, especially in Nigeria, where many special education schools lack trained teachers, electricity, internet, or even basic teaching materials (Lynch, Singal and Francis, 2022). Thus, the use and implementation of an adaptive learning system would be more effective when accompanied by broader systemic reforms.

2.3 Adaptive Learning Systems and Individual Needs of Students with Learning Disabilities

Students with learning disabilities in special education schools are a heterogeneous group, which represents a wide range of behavioural, cognitive, sensory and emotional needs (Balami, Oparaugo and Dimshaka, 2023). Some may struggle with reading (dyslexia), others with numeracy (dyscalculia), and some with attention and executive functioning (ADHD or autism disorders) (Alkhaldeh, Ahmad and Khasawneh, 2021; Al-Dokhny, Bukhamseen and Drwish, 2022; Thawalampola *et al.*, 2024). Unfortunately, a “one-size-fits-all” curriculum is usually unable to accommodate this kind of variation (Alkhaldeh, Ahmad and Khasawneh, 2021).

The adaptive learning systems provide a platform through which instruction can be modified to meet the unique profile of each student with learning disabilities, by utilising artificial intelligence, learner analytics, and real-time feedback systems (Gligorea *et al.*, 2023). For instance, an adaptive reading platform like the Lexia Reading Programme has been proven to be suitable for students with reading difficulties (Ness, Couperus and Wiley, 2013; Hurwitz and Vanacore, 2022). The LR Programme places students at a level that matches their abilities while the students use headphones to facilitate auditory learning (Ness, Couperus and Wiley, 2013).

However, despite the advantages of adaptive learning systems, the technology is not without some limitations. One of these is the fact that adaptive learning systems often rely on a limited scope of assessment, typically right-or-wrong responses, to assess student performance, which may not capture other aspects of learning such as creativity, teamwork, and emotional intelligence (Vaida, 2020; Gligorea *et al.*, 2023). Similarly, a

student with ADHD may perform poorly not because they did not understand, but rather because they have a momentary lapse in attention, which the adaptive system may interpret as a cognitive gap and oversimplify the content, which would hinder the student's learning process (Vaida, 2020). In conclusion, adaptive learning systems are an effective approach to meeting the needs of students with learning disabilities. However, for this system to be effective in Nigeria, it must be designed with continual flexibility, pedagogical flexibility, and ethical awareness.

2.4 Key Learning Challenges Faced by Students with Learning Disabilities

There are several learning challenges encountered by students with learning disabilities, especially in Nigeria, which are further compounded by systemic, infrastructural, cultural, and pedagogical challenges; and collectively they act as barriers to equitable and meaningful education (Orim and Udie, 2023).

One of the foremost challenges is the misconception of the disability. Regular teachers, parents, and the general public do not consider learning disabilities to be a special needs condition because there is no sensory or physical evidence of them; especially for children with dysgraphia, where many people in society believe it is not a disability but rather a child's lack of seriousness or being a slow-learner (Orim and Udie, 2023). In addition, there are limited specialised support services for students with special needs, such as speech and language therapy, as well as the lack of trained teachers for students with learning disabilities (Ojiegbe and Ekwueme, 2023).

Furthermore, the rigidity of the curriculum (which rarely accommodates the slower pacing or extended practice needed by students with disabilities), inadequate infrastructural materials (such as large print books, adaptive writing instruments, speech-to-text software, etc), and classroom and teacher-student ratio (which limits the teacher's ability to provide individualised attention) are some of those challenges that students with learning disabilities face (Mosia and Phasha, 2017; Barrett *et al.*, 2019; Frost *et al.*, 2025).

However, beyond the infrastructural and instructional barriers, there exists the psychological challenge caused by societal stigma and parental attitudes. Unfortunately, in many Nigerian communities, learning disabilities are poorly perceived to be signs of laziness, demonic influence, or intellectual inferiority (Ojiegbe and Ekwueme, 2023). This misclassification affects how the students with learning disabilities are treated by their peers and teachers, and also influences how parents engage with the education process; some parents might withdraw their children from school entirely thinking that formal education is a waste of time (Orim and Udie, 2023; Ojiegbe and Ekwueme, 2023). Hence, the reason why we have many out-of-school students with learning disabilities (Parveen, Kamal and Mushtaq, 2023).

Despite these challenges, the Nigerian government has been putting in efforts to curb some of these issues. For instance, the Dyslexia Foundation of Nigeria and the Learn Ability Initiative are interventions that combine teacher workshops, adaptive technology, and community sensitisation to improve outcomes for students with learning disabilities (Rahamat *et al.*, 2024).

2.5 Technological and Infrastructural Barriers to Implementing Adaptive Learning Systems in Special Education Schools

Adaptive learning systems usually thrive in environments with robust digital infrastructure; unfortunately, their implementation in Nigeria, precisely in public special schools, faces persistent barriers that are structural, financial and technical (Ajayi, Jacob and Ayoko, 2023). Inadequate funding of education, especially within the special needs sub-sector, is one of the major challenges militating against the effective implementation of adaptive learning systems (Ajayi, Jacob and Ayoko, 2023). Given that the UNESCO (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation) benchmark for the allocation of funds to education is 26%, Nigeria has, for the past 10 years, been underperforming by allocating an average of 5-8% (Shehu, 2024). Within this limited funding envelope, special education receives a disproportionately small share, and the ripple effect is manifested in poorly constructed or dilapidated classrooms, insufficient ICT resources, and, of course, a noticeable absence of adaptive learning technologies essential for inclusive instruction (Ajayi, Jacob and Ayoko, 2023).

More so, even where basic computing infrastructures are in place, the effective use and reliability of such technologies is another thing of concern, because of the non-existence or unstable electricity supply in many Nigerian special schools (Iniobong, 2025). Another challenge is the issue regarding digital illiteracy among teachers and school administrators to engage with adaptive learning systems meaningfully (Ajayi, Jacob and Ayoko, 2023). However, there have been notable efforts by the private sector, NGOs, and governments to bridge some of these gaps. For instance, several ICT hubs and initiatives have been launched by Huawei to support Nigeria's digital transformation (Richards, 2025). These efforts have aided the effective implementation of adaptive learning in Nigeria's special schools.

2.6 Theoretical Review

The design of adaptive learning systems for students with learning disabilities can best be understood through the lenses of relevant theoretical frameworks, which include the constructivist learning theory and the Universal Design for Learning (UDL).

2.6.1 Constructivist Theory

The constructivist theory, rooted in the works of Piaget (1972) and Vygotsky (1978), posits that people tend to build their knowledge based on an interplay between what they already know and believe and the knowledge with which they interact (Chand, 2023). Constructivism is all about learners constructing their knowledge instead of passively taking in information (University of Buffalo, 2024). The theory applies to adaptive learning systems, which provide personalised means where students build on past knowledge and progress at their own pace. In special education, constructivism provides a compelling rationale for doing away with one-size-fits-all teaching methods (University of Buffalo, 2024). A learner with autism, for instance, might need structured feedback and predictable routines to lessen cognitive overload, whereas a student with dyslexia might benefit from audio-visual scaffolding in a reading model (Thwala, 2018). Thus, constructivist theory puts these ideas into practice by adjusting the form and sequence of content based on learner data.

However, the constructivist theory has been criticised for assuming a level of learner independence and metacognitive ability that may not exist in all cases (Arik and Yilmaz, 2020). Constructivist models may falter in some scenarios where many students with disabilities have limited exposure to digital tools and may lack foundational literacy or numeracy skills unless supported by well-trained teachers who can facilitate the learner's navigation of the digital content (Arik and Yilmaz, 2020).

2.6.2 Universal Design for Learning (UDL) Theory

The Universal Design for Learning (UDL), developed by CAST (Centre for Applied Special Technology) in the 1990s, is another theory relevant to this study. The UDL is an educational framework that offers a range of representation, action, and expression methods to create inclusive learning environments that cater to the diverse needs of students (Meyer et al., 1998). The importance of designing curricula, instruction, and assessments that take into consideration the varied needs, preferences, and abilities of learners is strongly emphasised by UDL theory (Vincent, Okeowo and Ariyo, 2024). It promotes the idea that learning environments should be flexible and adaptive to accommodate a variety of learning styles, interests, and readiness levels (Meyer et al., 2014).

In this study, applying UDL principles entails considering the diverse needs and preferences of students with disabilities when implementing adaptive learning systems in special education schools in Nigeria. Also, applying Universal Design for Learning (UDL) principles to this study means examining how adaptive learning systems in special education schools offer a range of representational tools, like text-to-speech features, alternative formats for visual content, or tactile representations, to help students with disabilities understand and access information (Vincent, Okeowo and Ariyo, 2024). However, the UDL theory would be difficult to implement in an environment that lacks adequate funding or investment (Scott, 2018).

2.7 Empirical Review

A study by Vincent, Okeowo and Ariyo (2024) explored the utilisation of adaptive learning systems for learners with disabilities in Ondo State technical colleges. The study included

104 participants (38 lecturers and 66 students with disabilities) and utilised a qualitative approach to analyse the data. Vincent, Okeowo and Ariyo (2024) discovered the availability of adaptive learning technologies for students with disabilities in the Ondo State Technical Colleges; however, their utilisation is limited. It was therefore recommended that access to these technologies be increased.

Okoye (2024) examined the role of assistive technology in enhancing the inclusivity of children with disabilities in Nigeria. The study adopted the survey research design and thematic analysis, and one-sample t-statistics was used to analyse the data. Okoye (2024) portrayed how important assistive technology is in enabling inclusive educational opportunities for children with disabilities by giving them the resources they require to participate in schooling and actively engage in the process of learning. Additionally, it was discovered that learning challenges in math, writing, and reading are addressed by assistive technology (Okoye, 2024).

Similarly, the study on the availability and use of adaptive or assistive technology for learning was carried out by Olumorin, Babalola and Amoo (2022). The study was carried out among 100 special students in Kwara State for social needs. The study showed that assistive technologies are available for all the special students in the school, and about 48% of the students frequently use the tools. The study, therefore, recommended that the Ministry of Education should put in place seminars, workshops, conferences, and training for special education teachers (Olumorin, Babalola and Amoo, 2022).

2.8 Research Gap

Despite a growing body of global literature on adaptive learning systems and inclusive education, significant gaps persist, particularly in their application within Nigerian special education contexts. One of the research gaps is a methodological gap, which is very apparent. Much of the available Nigerian literature (Olumorin, Babalola and Amoo, 2022; Ojiegbe and Ekwueme, 2023; Rahamat *et al.*, 2024; Vincent, Okeowo and Ariyo, 2024) on adaptive learning systems in special education relies heavily on descriptive survey designs, which, while useful for gauging awareness and attitudes, do not provide deep insights into causality, impact, or user experience (Vincent, Okeowo and Ariyo, 2024).

Thus, there is a need for more experimental, longitudinal, and qualitative case studies that assess not only whether adaptive learning works, but also how, why, and under what conditions it can be sustainably integrated into the daily routines of special education schools.

2.9 Conclusion

Engaging with the studies discussed in this section of this research has strengthened and refined the research questions (what are the key learning challenges faced by students with learning disabilities in Nigerian special education schools?; what technological and infrastructural barriers exist in implementing adaptive learning systems in Nigerian special education schools?; how can an adaptive learning system be tailored to meet the individual needs of students with various types of learning disabilities?) by providing empirical support and contextual clarity. These studies confirm that while adaptive and assistive technologies are available in some Nigerian schools, their utilisation is inconsistent and often limited due to infrastructural, training, and access challenges. As a result, the initial question on learning challenges has become more focused on the practical accessibility and functional usage of adaptive systems. The inquiry into technological and infrastructural barriers is now better supported by evidence showing limited training and underutilisation among educators and students. Additionally, the question about tailoring adaptive systems has been reinforced by findings that suggest the need for differentiated tools to address specific disabilities, such as difficulties in reading, writing, and mathematics. These insights have not only validated the significance of the research questions but also highlighted the urgency of exploring practical implementation strategies.

Consequently, this chapter looks at the currently existing themes that were highlighted in the course of the research while discussing these themes backed up with diverse works by other authors. Furthermore, the themes that involve the concept of adaptive learning systems, adaptive learning systems and learning disabilities in special education schools, learning challenges faced by students with learning disabilities and barriers in implementing adaptive learning systems in special education schools were discussed in

this research topic, while crafting a research gap for the subject under investigation. As a result, the subsequent chapter will look at the methodology that was chosen, which includes the research philosophy, research approach, design, sampling, data collection and analysis.

Chapter Three

Research Methodology

3.0 Introduction

This chapter covered the research methodology for the current scholarly work, the population being studied, the sampling method, the instrument for data collection, the analysis of data, the reliability and validity of data collection tools, study philosophy, study design, and ethical considerations about the study. Hence, Figure 3.1 study Onion reflects how the research methodology employed in the study aligns with the paradigm by Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2019).

Figure 3 1: Research Onion (Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2019).

3.1 Research Philosophy

Research philosophy is the underlying structure of a methodology, i.e., the ontological and epistemological aspects (Avenier and Thomas, 2015). Wilson (2014) claims that research philosophy governs the approach used while researching to enable interpretation and comprehension of the results of the study. Furthermore, Ragab and

Arisha (2018) state that research philosophy is a set of perceptions that are interested in the structuring of data acquired through inquiry. Thus, three philosophic positions (ontology and epistemology) have been identified to be included in this study and were used in solving the philosophical aspect of this study.

3.1.1 Ontology

In social sciences, ontology is the concept postulating that a study phenomenon arises as an independent entity irrespective of what a researcher contributes or observes (Lauer, 2019). Ontology, as Maarouf (2019) describes, interrogates whether to view interpersonal events as objective or subjective. Objectivism argues that social events and their corresponding concepts exist independently of the roles and views of social actors (Klakegg, 2016). Further, losifides (2018) argued that the actions and thoughts of social agents explain why social phenomena exist and this leads to subjectivism in them. This research adopts subjectivism as its ontological viewpoint based on the objective of the present study, which is to examine the Design of an Adaptive Learning System for Students with Learning Disabilities in Nigerian Special Education Schools. This research adopts subjectivism as its ontological viewpoint based on the objective of the study, which is to examine the design of an adaptive learning system for Students with Learning Disabilities in Nigerian Special Education Schools. Following Levitt et al. (2022) claims, subjective ontology allows study results to be shaped by individuals' perceptions and actions, particularly with a focus on comprehending the interpretive meaning given to these occurrences. Thus, this will help in investigating individuals' perceptions and opinions in a quest to interpret this study's results (losifides, 2018).

3.1.2 Epistemology

Epistemology, according to Moon and Blackman (2014), is a matter of how individuals can know the true nature of a problem and the boundaries of human knowledge. Positivism and interpretivism are broadly accepted epistemic stances researchers have adopted (Belharar et al., 2023). Positivism is a philosophy that examines things observable and draws hypotheses based on empirical facts (Mathotaarachchi and Thilakarathna, 2021). Additionally, positivism lays strong emphasis on an objective analysis of facts and sound evidence in attempting to minimize the influence of subjective

impressions and biased human views (Flis, 2019). Interpretivism, on the contrary, concentrates on subjective views, which recognize individual distinctness about real events since humans can provide subjective opinions and judgments (Yanow, 2015). Interpretivism considers several factors, such as national differences and other determinative factors restructuring people's experiences (Alharahsheh and Pius, 2020). Thus, the positivism and interpretivism approaches can complement each other, offering approaches that can be suitable for a study's research objectives.

This research employed an interpretive philosophical stance congruent with the study's purpose, seeking to evaluate the design of an adaptive learning system for students with learning disabilities in Nigerian special education schools. Employing an interpretive epistemological stance can help to enhance the comprehension of individual thoughts and feelings, allowing for an examination of the opinions and beliefs of respondents towards an adaptive learning system. The interpretative philosophical approach places a strong emphasis on people's interpretations of events as well as the intricate structure of knowledge (Elbardan et al., 2017). To comprehend the underlying facts and motivations that shape what is observed and the connection between the Adaptive Learning System and Learning Disabilities in Nigerian Special Education Schools, an interpretative philosophical approach might carefully analyze several circumstances and aspects.

3.2 Research Approach

This study employed an abductive approach in examining the information collected. Awuzie and Dermott (2017) argue that the employment of an abductive approach in qualitative research is important as it allows researchers to gain a more profound understanding or reveal novel processes or events. The abductive process is a logical inference encompassing extensive understanding to facilitate the creation of new information relating to a specific phenomenon being examined (Thompson, 2022). Thus, it allows an investigator to make sensible conclusions from the data collected synthesize, and analyze it to provide a better explanation of the phenomena under investigation (Thompson, 2022). The abductive approach also combines experimental and theoretical aspects by embracing both the inductive and deductive methods (Okoli, 2021). Thus, while gathering or analyzing experimental data and developing the framework, an

abductive strategy can enable an investigator to alternate among several methods and properly integrate them (Vila-Henninger et al., 2022). The systematic assembly allows for creating relationships between facts and a novel hypothesis as well as expanding their understanding (Vila-Henninger et al., 2022). Therefore, to conduct comprehensive research on the design of an adaptive learning system for students with learning disabilities in Nigerian special education schools, an abductive approach was employed. This approach allows me to conclude when merging and analysing empirical facts. Moreover, I employed the abductive approach as it will enable me to switch between theories and empirical findings, combine them, translate them, and finally give a more detailed explanation of the subject matter at hand.

3.3 Research Design

According to Tengli (2020), the research design is a general plan for a research study that has 3 different yet interrelated elements: the investigation's approach, the timeframe, and the methodical decision. Tengli (2020) states that a research design simplifies the description of the types of evidence required, the way data will be gathered and analyzed, and how best to address the study questions. In addition to this, the primary goal of a research design is to ensure that the data gathered enables me to answer those questions as precisely as possible. The study design method was categorized into three classes by Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2019) in their onion model study: mixed-methods, qualitative, and quantitative design. As stated by Creswell (2014), the quantitative design has the limitation of underrepresenting the complexity of the methods involved, though it could offer an extremely high degree of accuracy and precision in addition to being used to measure assumptions and the correlation between various variables. As Creswell and Plano (2018) state, the mixed method takes more time and is even harder to implement, yet it might ensure a broader epistemological understanding of the issue under investigation.

Furthermore, a qualitative study design is a data collection study conducted by a researcher to determine the genuine views of several people on a particular topic (Tengli, 2020). This could be immensely helpful in the sense that it provides room for respondents to state their views, sentiments, attitudes, and results. Denzin and Lincoln (2000) take a

stand that a qualitative research design is a descriptive and interpretive process that handles the periods under study in a wider context. Yin (2013) contends that an inquiry may be deemed exhaustive when it can establish the root causes of different outcomes and their interconnections, particularly when the final concern is the interconnections between the causes and consequences.

As Barrett and Twycross (2018) argue, this qualitative research method also provides respondents with a way of seeking clarification in case they are unsure of what questions are being asked of them. This being the case, the study takes into account the use of qualitative research design as a way of allowing the special education school teachers in Lagos Nigeria which serves as the study participants to openly and truthfully participate in a discussion of their experiences about the design of an adaptive learning system and learning disabilities. Thus, I was able to collect ample amounts of data from a sizable number of people through an online interview method. The main advantage of this online interview method, according to Babbie (2016), is that it can offer plenty of data efficiently and at a faster rate. However, this comes with several weaknesses such as a possibility of unrepresentative response, a lack of qualitative information, and a weak capacity to address complex questions appropriately as noted by Babbie (2016).

Furthermore, a study research design can be divided into two broad categories based on the time horizons and this includes longitudinal studies and cross-sectional studies (Bryman and Bell 2015). Caruana et al. (2015) posit that longitudinal studies refer to a study that tracks an event or a group of individuals over some time. Alternatively, cross-sectional research, also known as "a picture," is a single examination of a phenomenon or a representative sample of a whole community (Setia 2016). Hence, this research utilized a cross-sectional study research design based on time frame due to the nature of the participants involved which includes the teachers in special education schools in Nigeria.

3.4 Data Collection Method

To collect data, I employed semi-structured interviews. The interviews were carried out online through Google Meet video in English and at various times depending on the

interviewed participants' schedules. Open-ended questions were incorporated into semi-structured interviews that I designed to encourage a natural dialogue among them. Semi-structured interviews allow me to gain in-depth information about memories, ideas, beliefs, feelings, or motives concerning the events to be studied (DeJonckheere and Vaughn, 2019). Additionally, semi-structured interviews offer two-way communication of information between a researcher and the respondents interviewed and present an opportunity for researchers to ask supplementary questions to enable an in-depth insight into the responses provided by the respondents (Polit and Beck, 2017). To gain a better understanding of the design of an adaptive learning system and learning disabilities in Nigerian special education schools, I engaged in successful interviews with all the respondents. Each interview of each individual was carried out on Google Meet with the recording device and lasted between 10 to 20 minutes for each individual.

All conversations were conducted electronically, which gave respondents and researchers flexibility in schedule and helped them overcome distance-related challenges. However, before conducting the interviews, all participants received a briefing on the interview's dos and don'ts. Additionally, to avoid obtaining misleading answers from respondents, I conducted personal interviews first. The interview guide in Appendix 1 is a good way to conduct semi-structured interviews because it aims to provide direction and suggestions (Bell et al., 2018; Saunders et al., 2015). A structured interview guide offers a framework for the discussion and helps researchers stay focused on the primary subjects under investigation (Kallio et al., 2016). Moreover, it helps to gather data required to fulfill the purpose of the research which is to investigate the design of an adaptive learning system and learning disabilities in Nigerian special education schools. Dunwoodie et al. (2022) argue that following the interview guide exactly is necessary because it includes both planned and potentially significant questions, which allows me to gain a deeper understanding of the opinions of those who answered. As a result, I purposefully includes the most crucial questions in the interview guide to avoid receiving too many biased answers.

3.4.1 Respondent Criteria

The participants in the study were aged 18 years and above, and they included 10 teachers from different private Nigerian Special Education Schools who reside in Lagos State, Nigeria.

3.5 Population and Sampling Technique

The overall count of full-fledged nursery, primary and secondary special needs schools, according to the Nigerian government is 1,177 (EduCeleb, 2020). Because of this, it would be practically impossible to cover all special education school teachers in the study due to the large number of staff. Thus, a negligible number of ten teachers from five private special education schools in Lagos, Nigeria serves as the population of the study. Sampling procedures are crucial for research because they enable the selection of a smaller number of individuals or groups from a greater number of participants (Tengli et al., 2020). Different selection methods like area, rotary, snowball, random, and purposeful have been mentioned in the literature (Tengli et al., 2020). As Babbie (2016) asserts, random selection is widely utilized in quantitative research because it makes sure that each member of a group has an equal chance of being selected and provides a fair estimate of the whole population. It can be viable for very small sampling populations, though. Purposeful sampling, which has been defined by Palinkas et al. (2015), is useful to fewer people since it helps researchers choose people who can provide detailed and informative data. Purposive sampling, however, may yield an inaccurate sample if the process of selection is still unknown (Palinkas et al., 2015). Similarly, sampling techniques like snowballs, area, and rotating sampling may be skewed if specific requirements have not been met.

Despite this shared limitation, Babbie (2016) further states that rotary sampling encourages research where one needs to sample a subset of participants from a big sample. However, the locations of the research participants were ascertained through the process of purposeful sampling. Purposeful sampling is a technique used in qualitative research to choose interview subjects based on subject-relevant norms (Campbell et al., 2020). Thus, this study utilized purposeful sampling as it allows researchers to focus on particular respondents (e.g., private special school teachers) who have a higher level of

understanding of the problem, which can lead to the collection of more comprehensive and accurate data (Palinkas et al., 2015). As a result, using a purposeful sampling method helps me to talk to accessible and willing participants who supply relevant information at a convenient place and time.

3.6 Data Analysis

One of the most common qualitative research methods through which large complex data sets can be examined and interpreted is thematic analysis (Dawadi, 2020). Its application of value is in the manner it can recognize, examine, and synthesize trends or themes in qualitative data to inform a deeper understanding of the topic being researched (Maguire and Delahunt, 2017). By using this approach, I was able to know the general significance, feelings, and thoughts of the respondents (Mohajan, 2017). The thematic analysis provides a wide picture of the issue being studied, generating important conclusions and new conceptual frameworks by classifying data into themes and patterns of occurrence (Kampira, 2021). Thematic analysis is a systematic and adaptive method for revealing qualitative data richness and depth (Kampira, 2021). This makes it worthwhile for researchers to be aware of respondents' individual experiences and perspectives.

Thematic analysis is a versatile and robust qualitative analysis technique that has the potential to identify, investigate, and document trends (themes) underlying qualitative data (Dawadi, 2020). According to Maguire and Delahunt (2017), theme analysis provides a methodical and exploratory way to comprehend the complex relationship between learning disabilities in Nigerian special education schools and the design of an adaptive learning system (Maguire and Delahunt, 2017). This analysis helps research issues with few known empirical paradigms and seeks out themes by examining the data itself (Mohajan, 2017). Thus, this serves as a rich technique to investigate adaptive learning distinctive procedures and methods and Learning Disabilities in Nigerian Special Education Schools (Naeem et al., 2023).

Furthermore, this analysis is suitable for qualitative research as it facilitates a close inspection of teachers' responses, views, and actions in the design of an adaptive learning system and learning disabilities. I was able to analyse and comprehend the rich, context-

based information obtained. Furthermore, there is a need to highlight the parallels and differences between the methods employed by different special education schools in Nigeria to support the analytical choice. For researchers looking to comprehend respondents, this analysis offers a thorough grasp of trends and insights into the Design of an Adaptive Learning System and Learning Disabilities in Nigerian Special Education Schools.

The study was able to collect primary qualitative data from interviews developed with the research's intended objectives. At the end of the interview, the material used to collect the interview was translated upon reading it multiple times to look for any trends or patterns that might be used to improve the topic, which is part of the thematic analysis procedure (Nowell et al., 2017). A very important stage in thematic analysis is coding, where it takes down important ideas, facts, and trends the respondents emphasized (Mohajan, 2017). The codes that reflected similar relationships were then put into themes, allowing me to see themes and patterns. As a result, this technique was beneficial in learning how the design of an adaptive learning system was adopted by Nigerian special education schools.

3.7 Reliability and Validity

Reliability is the precision or dependability of the statistical techniques used, along with any individual or study procedural biases that may have been involved in influencing the outcomes (Noble and Smith, 2015). Saunders et al. (2015) contended that when conducting research on a dynamic ever-changing or complicated phenomenon by using semi-structured interviews, reliability can be challenging to establish, particularly for inexperienced researchers. Coleman (2021) also stated that consistency is made more difficult for a new researcher performing qualitative research when there is no clear consensus on the measurements to use. While semi-structured interviews pose a challenge for demonstration, researchers can enhance reliability by considering personal biases that may have influenced the findings, acknowledging biases that exist in data collection methods, and making an effort not to exhibit them (Noble and Smith, 2015).

Validity in qualitative research refers to the truth and precision of scientific evidence (Leung, 2015). To exclude any bias in analyzing the results of this study, the views of the participants who took part were taken with accuracy and clarity in the results without changing their implications. Responses to questions during interviews were precisely distilled into a few brief sentences. Though most of the respondents' words were correctly recorded and shortened, a few were emphasised using quotation marks to ensure correct reading and implications as per Rosenthal's (2016) instructions. I took some precautionary measures to avoid biased interpretation and intentional data manipulation.

3.8 Research Ethics

Ethics involves the study of what is right and acceptable in society, and what rules one should follow to uphold such standards (Resnik, 2020). This study data collection begins with seeking permission while ensuring that the privacy and identity of the subjects in the study are maintained. . In line with the British Educational Research Association (BERA, 2024) ethical guidelines, the study upheld core principles including respect for persons, justice, beneficence, and the minimisation of harm. The provision of forms for securing ethical permission and their filling also occurs while maintaining the confidentiality of the subjects through the prevention of the request for personal information. Thus, ethical approval was obtained from the appropriate ethics committee, reflecting compliance with both institutional requirements and BERA's (2024) standards for educational research integrity.

3.9 Summary

This section has looked at the significance and outcomes of the methodology that were carefully selected by me and their effectiveness was evaluated through careful analysis. I gave the most importance to choosing an appropriate study philosophy, approach, design, data collection and analysis procedures, sample strategies, and addressing the ethical issues with validity and reliability. The methodological techniques were chosen based on the dimensions, nature, and study type of questions and objectives. Hence, the following chapter will elaborate on the data collection, analysis and findings of the study.

Chapter Four

Findings and Discussion

4.0 Introduction

This chapter focuses on the analysis, presentation, and interpretation of the research findings, as well as the discussion of the findings in relation to existing literature and theories. Essentially, this chapter seeks to address the research questions, which include what are the key learning challenges faced by students with learning disabilities in Nigerian special education schools?; what technological and infrastructural barriers exist in implementing adaptive learning systems in Nigerian special education schools?; and how can an adaptive learning system be tailored to meet the individual needs of students with various types of learning disabilities? Hence, the findings are presented in accordance with these objectives.

4.1 Learning challenges faced by students with learning disabilities → RQ1

Under this objective, two key themes emerged from the analysis of the interview data. These themes highlight the challenges faced by students with learning disabilities in Nigerian special education schools. The themes are synthesised in Table 4.1.

Table 4 1: Learning challenges faced by students with learning disabilities

Challenges	Themes
Challenge 1	Cognitive/behavioural challenges
Challenge 2	Communication/social difficulties

4.1.1 Cognitive/behavioural challenges

Cognitive/behavioural challenges were highlighted as a major theme during the interviews. The majority of the interviewees stated that teaching students with learning disabilities is a very challenging task because these students have difficulty with understanding, heeding to instructions and remembering things. This in turn affects their

learning in general as they find it hard to read, spell, or solve simple mathematical problems. The findings also revealed that the students exhibit behaviours like frustration and inability to focus and sit still to learn. These behavioural issues compound the problems for instructors and contribute to the struggle in the learning process. Some of the interview excerpts that highlight these cognitive/behavioural challenges include:

Mr A: "Most of my students find it hard to understand instructions the first time... They find it hard to read and spell, even when they try their best."

Mr B: "They find it difficult to follow step-by-step instructions, especially in subjects like mathematics."

Mr E: "Many of them struggle to remember what they were taught the previous day. Retention is a big issue."

Mr D: "They have serious difficulty with basic math concepts like counting...They get frustrated because they can't keep up with their peers. It affects their confidence..."

Mr F: "I have students who can't sit still or focus for more than a few minutes."

These excerpts indicate the prevalence of cognitive/behavioural challenges among students with learning disabilities in Nigerian special education schools.

4.1.2 Communication/social difficulties

Another challenge observed among students with learning disabilities in Nigerian special education schools is the issue of communication/social interaction. It has been observed that these children find it hard to socialise or even share their thoughts. This is particularly owing to issues with speaking clearly or the lack of self-esteem. According to a teacher (Mr I): *"Peer pressure affects them... when others laugh at their mistakes, they withdraw."* As a result, they are often quiet in class, keeping to themselves instead of asking questions and interacting with the instructor. Other excerpts from which this theme was coined are as follows:

Mr C: “Some of my students can’t express themselves clearly, so they often keep quiet even when they’re confused.”

Mrs G: “I see quite a few students with autism spectrum disorder... challenges with social interaction and communication.”

Mrs H: “I’ve worked with students who are very intelligent but can’t express their thoughts.”

Therefore, communication/social difficulties are a significant challenge to both the learning environment and education of students with learning disabilities in Nigerian special education schools.

4.2 Technological and infrastructural barriers → RQ2

Under this objective, five key themes emerged from the analysis of the interview data. These themes highlight the technological and infrastructural barriers that teachers face when implementing adaptive learning systems in Nigerian special education schools. The themes are synthesised in Table 4.2.

Table 4 2: Technological and infrastructural barriers

Barriers	Themes
Barrier 1	Lack of digital infrastructure
Barrier 2	Unreliable electricity and internet access
Barrier 3	Poor learning environment
Barrier 4	Lack of government and policy support
Barrier 5	Limited teacher training on technology use

4.2.1 Lack of digital infrastructure

The lack of digital infrastructure was found to be a key barrier to the implementation of adaptive learning systems in Nigerian special education schools. The significance of this barrier lies in the fact that adaptive learning systems are greatly dependent on digital infrastructure like computers, tablets, and other electronic devices. Hence, where these devices are lacking, adaptive learning systems cannot take root. The insights were shared by some of the interviewees as follows:

Mr A: "In my school, we don't have access to any computers or tablets."

Mrs G: "Many students have never even touched a computer."

Mr I: "We still rely on posters, flashcards, and manual teaching aids."

These excerpts show that there is still a great digital gap in these schools, and as such, the implementation of adaptive learning systems cannot be effective until these concerns are addressed through the provision of these digital infrastructures.

4.2.2 Unreliable electricity and internet access

Also, there is the issue of unreliable electricity and internet, which is characteristic of the region in which these schools exist. Without reliable electricity and internet, it is impossible to adequately utilise digital tools for adaptive learning. According to the interviewees:

Mr B: "We don't have electricity most of the time, let alone devices."

Mr D: "Internet is a major issue. Even if we had devices, there's no reliable connection."

Mr E: "There's no backup power, and I can't charge my phone at school."

Thus, this unreliable electricity and internet access serve as a critical barrier to the implementation of adaptive learning systems in Nigerian special education schools since both electricity and internet connection play a major role in enabling adaptive learning.

4.2.3 Poor learning environment

Another major theme under this category is the state of the learning environment. Interviewees have claimed that the learning environment is poor for conducive learning. Teachers cite that the buildings are debilitated and not well-ventilated, and the classrooms are tiny and harbour a large number of students:

Mrs G: "Our classrooms are overcrowded and not well-ventilated."

Mr J: "The walls are peeling, roofs leak, and dust gets everywhere."

Another interviewee stated, *"The classroom has no sockets or stable surfaces to set up a projector"* (Mr F). Together, these issues hinder the setup of adaptive learning systems and do not even permit conducive learning.

4.2.4 Lack of government and policy support

Another factor that hinders the implementation of adaptive learning systems in Nigerian special education schools is the lack of government and policy support. Due to the cost of implementing adaptive learning systems for individuals with learning disabilities, in many cases, schools are not able to fund the project, requiring additional funding from the government and other entities. However, it has been disclosed by the teachers that there is a dearth of government funding or support towards the implementation of adaptive learning systems in Nigerian special education schools. According to the interviewees:

Mr A: "Honestly, I haven't seen any direct government support in my school."

Mrs H: "We rely more on NGO support than the government."

Mr J: "We've written letters and proposals, but nothing has been done to help us implement anything adaptive."

The lack of policies directed towards the betterment of education in Nigerian special education schools is also significant. This is owing to the fact that these policies are supposed to help direct support towards these schools and foster the implementation of

adaptive learning systems in these schools. Ironically, the findings also revealed although there are quite a few policies directed towards Nigerian special education schools, they are rarely implemented. This viewpoint was shared by Mr D, who stated that *“Policies are there on paper, but implementation is the real problem.”* Hence, it is evident that the lack of government and policy support hinders the implementation of adaptive learning systems in Nigerian special education schools.

4.2.5 Limited teacher training on technology use

Furthermore, the study's findings revealed that there is limited teacher training on technology use in Nigerian special education schools, which serves as a barrier to the implementation of adaptive learning systems in these schools. The teachers claimed that they do not possess the competence to effectively execute instructions using adaptive learning systems, and have not been given the proper training to help them do so. Some of the interview excerpts that portray this theme include:

Mr E: “I haven’t been trained on how to use technology effectively in teaching.”

Mr C: “We had a digital literacy workshop, but not for adaptive learning tools.”

Mr F: “To be honest, I’m not sure how adaptive learning systems function technically.”

This is significant because these teachers are the personnel that handle the digital systems to educate the students. Hence, not having the technical know-how to navigate these tools implies that adaptive learning cannot be implemented even if the infrastructure is provided.

4.3 Tailoring adaptive systems to individual needs → RQ3

Under this objective, four key themes emerged from the analysis of the interview data. These themes highlight recommendations on how adaptive learning systems can be tailored to meet the individual needs of students with various types of learning disabilities. The themes are synthesised in Table 4.3.

Table 4 3: Strategies for tailoring adaptive systems to individual needs

Strategies	Themes
Strategy 1	Differentiated instructional strategies
Strategy 2	Multisensory and inclusive teaching
Strategy 3	Local adaptation
Strategy 4	Caregiver involvement

4.3.1 Differentiated instructional strategies

This theme portrays the significance of utilising different teaching strategies that are supportive of the diverse cognitive and learning needs of the students with learning disabilities. The interviewees reported the advantages of decomposing tasks, speeding up or slowing down lesson pace, using visual media and narrations, and offering students other forms of expression (such as oral or drawing their answers). Some of the excerpts mirroring these insights include:

Mr A: "I break lessons into smaller steps and go at a slower pace."

Mr B: "Personally, I use a lot of visual aids... it makes learning more concrete."

Mr D: "I often use storytelling and role-playing."

Mr F: "I allow oral responses or use drawing as an alternative."

These strategies simply illustrate the main tenet of adaptive learning systems by personalising the delivery of content. Practically, in adaptive systems, learners need different formats of inputs, levels of difficulty of tasks, and timeliness. This theme implies that variations in strategy of teachers who implement differentiated approaches on an informal basis should be represented in the successful design of adaptation technologies.

4.3.2 Multisensory and inclusive teaching

The teachers also highlighted that they used some visual, audible, and tactile resources to meet the sensory needs of the students. This indicates that the adaptive systems need to be multi-modal, capable of interchanging the visual aids, audio instructions, and interactive tasks according to the strength or the disability of each learner. Inclusivity also implies the creation of systems with the ability to modify not just pace but also mode of engagement. Some of the interview excerpts that portray this theme include:

Mr E: "I mix audio, visual, and hands-on activities."

Mrs G: "I try to observe each student closely and adjust my instructions."

Mrs H: "I use frequent assessments to know where they're struggling."

These interview excerpts underscore the adaptive learning environment, which monitors patterns of learning progress and suggests the necessary sensory tools according to the individual to keep them focused and facilitate better understanding.

4.3.3 Local adaptation

Educators emphasised the importance of systems being culturally and contextually suitable. They echoed that they do not seek "copy-paste" solutions contributed by the global context but tools that are locally relevant developed collaboratively with the special educators. According to some of the teachers:

Mr A: "I hope that in the future, adaptive learning tools will be more available and tailored to our students' specific needs."

Mrs H: "Personally, I believe adaptive learning has great potential, but only if rural and special schools are not left behind."

This theme points to the importance of co-design; teachers, parents, and learners must be involved in the design of how the system is constructed, making sure it reflects the truth on the ground with regard to Nigerian special education schools. The results also imply that training, infrastructure, implementation of policies and long-term partnerships

between the government and the private sector are necessary to attain successful adaptive learning in the long term.

4.3.4 Caregiver involvement

This theme demonstrates that home-based assistance is essential in order to reinforce the learning process, but still most of the caregivers in such communities cannot access these mechanisms due to the lack of knowledge, literacy or technological base to engage in any adaptive learning plans. This was cited by several teachers:

Mr B: "Most parents are not involved at all because they don't understand how the technology works."

Mr C: "Many of the parents I interact with are not literate..."

Mrs G: "Some parents are afraid of technology and think it might harm their child."

This implies that for the implementation of adaptive learning systems to be effective, caregivers must be involved in the students' education. Hence, adaptive learning systems need to be simple, low-bandwidth, mobile-friendly and in local languages if possible. The teachers also advise that the caregivers should be trained and sensitised in order to help them use technology at home. With no thoughtful parent or carer involvement, personalised learning outside of the classroom will be threatened. System designers therefore need to take into account both user-based usability and home-based usability, particularly in the low-income/low-literacy environments.

4.4 Discussion

The study's findings are congruent with and contribute meaningfully to extant literature. The findings revealed two learning challenges faced by students with learning disabilities, namely cognitive/behavioural challenges and communication/social difficulties. These results are in line with the previous studies that indicate that students with learning disabilities are likely to demonstrate memory retention, task completion, interpretation, attention, and social interaction shortcomings (Ojiegbe and Ekwueme, 2023; Orim and Udie, 2023). According to the findings, the most fundamental tasks in learning, such as

reading, spelling and arithmetic, are hampered by delays in processing and behavioural frustrations. This conforms to the constructivist position in which learning is very much social and relies immensely on sensible interaction, which is one of the aspects that is highly restrained in such situations.

In line with the constructivist learning theory, these challenges underscore the importance of learners making use of meaningful experiences in order to construct knowledge. Nevertheless, in the case where students do not make the effort to engage because of memory or attention problems, as disclosed in this study, the process of creating new knowledge is essentially interrupted. Similarly, the UDL premise, which promotes novelty in the manner in which the learners are introduced to and can relay information, endorses the significance of supporting such learning issues with multiple means of engagement, representation, and expression (Meyer, Rose and Gordon, 2014). The identification of communication and social challenges corresponds to the critique of Maslow's hierarchy of needs by McLeod (2007) that portrays that psychological and social needs are most prominent in collectivist societies and they must be addressed before there can be successful learning.

The findings also highlighted that the lack of digital infrastructure, unreliable electricity and internet, poor learning environment, lack of government/policy support, and limited teacher training on technology hinder the implementation of adaptive learning systems. These results are amplified by the findings of Ajayi, Jacob and Ayoko (2023), who found out that access to technology and infrastructural degradation are the main factors hindering digital learning in rural schools in Nigeria. Moreover, electricity and internet stability have also been recounted as periodical or unavailable in the UNESCO (2023) report on education systems in sub-Saharan Africa.

Notably, adaptive learning systems require unwavering access to devices and connections. From the lens of the UDL, the lack of multiple ways of content delivery because of infrastructural shortages does not allow student interaction in the manner that suits their learning profiles. Likewise, the constructivist learning theory has a strong stance on learning by interacting and exploration; though, in the absence of the tools that

would allow such interaction, constructivist learning is hindered. Furthermore, the lack of training of teachers in adaptive technologies has a very serious impact on using any inclusive system. This is also indicated in the findings of Butera et al. (2020), who argue that effective reforms should give power to teachers as the change agents. This also shows that the teacher capacity-building program is urgent, and it is an element of the international best practices, including the Tusome project in Kenya that concentrated on the infrastructure and teacher development parts to enhance better literacy outcomes (Piper et al., 2016).

Differentiated instructional strategies, multisensory and inclusive teaching, local adaptation, and involvement of the caregivers were also cited as key strategies for tailoring adaptive learning systems to meet the individual needs of students with various types of learning disabilities. These strategies coincide with the UDL principles promoting the idea of multiple paths to learning, which are the input, processing, and output (Navaitiene and Stasiūnaitienė, 2021). The informal adaptive techniques used by teachers confirm the possibilities of formal adaptive systems, which can extend these activities and provide the students with the monitoring, feedback, and progression on the basis of consistency. According to Meyer, Rose and Gordon (2014), high-quality learning environments should be perceptually and linguistically diverse, which can be achieved through automation and individualisation of adaptive platforms with an appropriate design.

The demand for local adaptation of systems also lends itself well to both theoretical frameworks. Based on a constructivist perspective, learning may be considered as meaningful when the content is contextualised in terms of the cultural and social realities of learners (Tobias and Duffy, 2009). Educators emphasised that tools, which are not only imported, need to be based on the experiences of learning and teaching Nigerian learners and educators. This reflects Ulferts' (2021) policy recommendation against "top-down" policy approaches that ignore local needs.

Moreover, educators indicated that most of the parents are not digitally literate, do not understand digital technology in education, or have negative perceptions towards it. This

supports the result obtained by Okocha and Edafewotu (2022), who suggest low-bandwidth, mobile-friendly technologies that are local language-modified and parent training-supported. According to Vygotsky's (1978) constructivist philosophy, learning is a social construct and thus depends greatly on the support of caregivers as systems need to support students in different environments. In general, the findings confirm the relevance of a comprehensive, humanistic and contextual approach to educational interventions in Nigerian special education schools. Achieving this requires investment, policy implementation, and the co-creation of digital solutions with those who deal with special education firsthand.

4.5 Chapter Summary

This chapter presented and discussed the findings from interviews with ten teachers across five private special education schools in Lagos, Nigeria, in response to the study's three research questions. The findings revealed significant cognitive and social challenges faced by students with learning disabilities, as well as major infrastructural and technological barriers to implementing adaptive learning systems. Teachers also shared insightful strategies for tailoring adaptive technologies to meet students' individual needs, including differentiated instruction, multisensory teaching, local adaptation, and caregiver involvement. These findings provide a foundation for practical and policy recommendations, which are explored further in the concluding chapter.

This chapter has presented and discussed the study's findings. The results indicated major cognitive and social challenges faced by students with learning disabilities and a massive infrastructural and technological setback towards the implementation of adaptive learning systems. This chapter also highlighted key strategies for tailoring adaptive learning systems to meet the individual needs of students with various types of learning disabilities. The next chapter will provide an overall conclusion of the study.

Chapter Five

Conclusion

This research has provided an insight into the complicated realities of instructing students with learning disabilities in Nigeria special education schools and prospects of applying adaptive learning machines in order to improve the educational performance. Among the most important findings obtained, the fact that teacher use rather creative and resourceful instructional methods because of limited resources aligning with the principles of adaptive learning and UDL. Their unofficial access to differentiated work, visualisation, and multi-sensory strategy demonstrates the existence of a willingness to learn more formal, technology-assisted solutions if the infrastructure and training are provided. The findings contributes to the literature on the ways in which technology may be designed and implemented in low-resource special education settings.

The study supports the previous literary evidences on the cognitive and behaviour challenges that affect the students with disabilities learning including poor retention, lack of attention and frustration due to social comparison. Nevertheless, it also brings to the fore a poorly explored problem in the literature on Nigeria, which is the deep infrastructure and policy deficits that hinder the implementation of inclusive digital tools. For example, one could state that the fact that the majority of the schools do not even have the simplest devices or regular electricity proves the statements made by international organisations such as UNESCO, and highlights the situation indicating the necessity of urgent fund investments in special education. The results also showed that the caregivers are virtually inaccessible because of digital illiteracy and socio-economic factors, an aspect that demands immediate correction by means of training and the use of local language tools.

Reflecting on the research process, the qualitative design allowed me to obtain profound insights on the experience of teaching in special education. Though the sampling only included the private schools in Lagos, the depth of data was able to provide depth in understanding that would lead to further findings in the case of the general population in the wider research in other states or other categories of schools like the publicly funded schools. If repeated, the study should be triangulated with having the views of students

and caregivers added to the narrative. At a personal level, this study has transformed my ideas about inclusive education from being just an interventionary concept to a context-specific challenge requiring collaboration, innovation, and sustained advocacy.

Furthermore, there are robust implications of dissemination. School leaders and educational policy-makers will be presented with the findings of this research in the form of presentations, reports, or a journal article in the bid to advance knowledge in this field within low-resource environments. This research has further consolidated my resolve to promote affordable accessible inclusive learning technologies as a reality in special needs education in Nigeria and the world at large.

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Appendices

Appendix 1: Ethical Checklist Approval

The Design of an Adaptive Learning System for Students with Learning Disabilities in Nigerian Special Education Schools

Ethical Documents

Ethics Check List for Students conducting research under an approved class protocol

Programme of Study	MA in Education
Ethics UH Protocol number	0112 2024 Nov SSAH

RESEARCH PLAN: Specific information

Title of your study	Designing an Adaptive Learning System for Students with Learning Disabilities in Nigerian Special Education Schools
What is the total number of participants you are collecting data from?	10
What methods of collecting data are you using? (E.g. interviews, survey questionnaires, observations, etc)	Semi-structured interviews

Data will only be collected from adults who can provide informed consent. (If you intend to collect data from minors, please consult your supervisor to ensure this is permitted under this protocol).	Data will only be collected from adults who can provide informed consent.
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You should be able to answer 'Yes' to all these questions, where they are relevant to your research. If unsure of their relevance, you should consult your supervisor/module leader. Please complete the last section and return to your supervisor before starting your research

ENTERING THE FIELD:

I will explain clearly in writing/by email/verbally to participants the aims, purpose, and methods of my research.	Yes
I will obtain written/email permission for the collection of data from the locality (e.g. my workplace) where I will be collecting the data.	Yes
I will ensure that the participants give informed consent for their participation.	Yes

COLLECTING THE DATA

I will ensure that I only collect data relevant to my study and that my supervisor/delegated class protocol holder approves of my approach/questionnaire etc.	Yes
I will make sure that my research study is considered to be low-risk and that no aspect of my research will cause distress to my respondents. If my study is NOT considered to be low risk, I will ask my supervisor to submit an individual application for UH ethics approval (EC1A) on my behalf.	Yes

I will ensure that my methods of data collection and general approach match with the parameters set out in the approved class protocol.	Yes
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HOLDING AND PROCESSING (ANALYSING) THE DATA

I will ensure that all personal data is kept confidential and stored securely on the One Drive or in-locked file drawers.	Yes
I will ensure that data is only retained for as long as is necessary (usually until after the assessment is complete) and then securely destroyed.	Yes

REPORTING THE STUDY

I will ensure that all material relating to the data collection is anonymised (unless specifically asked not to do so), including all appended material.	Yes
I will be careful to use respectful language throughout my reporting.	Yes

Name of student: Oluwaseun Azeez

Student number: 23077169

Signature of student: OLUWASEUN AZEEZ

Date: 27/05/2025

Signature of supervisor:

Michael H. Young

Date: 12/06/2025

Appendix 2: Interview Transcripts

Interview 1

Interviewer: Hello, good evening and how are you doing?

Mr A: Yeah, I'm good.

Mr A: I'm good. You welcome

Interviewer: Right, I'm good as Okay, so first and foremost, I would like to appreciate you for honoring my invite to join the meeting. Thank you so much, sir. Yeah. All right. So, one thing I would like to add to or what I would let you know is that today's meeting is being recorded,...

Interviewer: but none of your personal information is going to be disclosed. Okay, sir.

Mr A: Okay. Hello.

Interviewer: All right. So, without further ado, let's move on to the first question, sir. All right.

Interviewer: So the first question goes, what are the most common types of learning disabilities you encounter among students in your school?

Interviewer: Hello. Can you hear me? Okay. What are the most common types of learning disabilities you encounter among students in your school?

Mr A: Yeah. Can you repeat that question?

Mr A: In my school, I mostly deal with students who have dyslexia. They find it hard to read and...

Mr A: spell even when they try their best. That's what I can say about that.

Interviewer: Okay.

Interviewer: All to Thank you so much for that response, sir. I really appreciate. What specific learning challenges do students with learning disabilities face on a daily basis?

Mr A: I would say most of my students find it hard to understand instructions. The first time I have to repeat and break things down severally for them.

Interviewer: Okay.

Interviewer: That is a nice answer. So, thanks for the feedback. the next question,...

Mr A: There we go. I would say I've seen that their academic progress is much slower than their peers.

Interviewer: how do these learning challenges affect students' academic progress and overall development?

Mr A: Even when they put in effort, they don't get the same results and that affects their self-esteem.

Interviewer: Okay.

Interviewer: That's a lovely response, Thanks again for the amazing feedback so far.

Interviewer: right, so the next question, sir, are you with me? All right. What teaching strategies have you found the most effective whenever you are trying to support your students that are with these learning disabilities?

Mr A: I'm with you.

Mr A: I would say how I have found breaking lessons into smaller steps and going at a slower pace helps my students understand better.

Interviewer: That's okay.

Interviewer: That's good. That's a nice way to make them understand better by breaking them into smaller steps. All right. So the next question sir,...

Interviewer: Can you tell us how accessible are technological tools for learning being in your school? Wow..

Mr A: In my school we don't have access to any computers or tablets. Most of the teaching is still done with chalk and board. That's it.

Interviewer: Thank you so much for that reply.

Interviewer: The next question, what infrastructural barriers have you encountered whenever you try to use educational technology in your classroom?

Mr A: One of the biggest issues for me is electricity. We hardly have power and during school hours, we hardly have power during school hours.

Mr A: So, I can't use any electric device even when I bring my own. Yeah, sure.

Interviewer: Okay.

Interviewer: Thank you so much. Moving on to the next question, sir. sir, how familiar are you with using adaptive learning systems and do you know how they function?

Mr A: And honestly,...

Interviewer: Okay. ...

Mr A: I'm not very familiar with Adaptive Learning Systems. However, I've heard the term before, but I don't really know how they work. That's just it.

Interviewer: All Moving on to the next question. How do you tailor your teaching method to suit students with different types of learning needs?

Mr A: What I do is I try to do my teaching by using visual aid songs and reading objects especially for students who don't respond well to just verbal explanations. In my experience,...

Interviewer: All thank you.

Interviewer: So much for the replies. the next question, so how involved are caregivers or parents in supporting the use of adaptive learning technologies at home or in the school?

Mr A: most parents are not involved because they don't understand how the technology works or how it can help their child.

Interviewer: All right. Moving on. What policy or government support is in place to allow schools like yours to implement adaptive learning technologies?

Mr A: I would say honestly I haven't seen any direct government support in my school for adaptive learning technologies.

Mr A: Most of what we use comes from our own efforts or NGO donations. Okay. What do you say concerning that?

Interviewer: Okay.

Interviewer: All right. which is the last question for today. Sir, what are your expectations for the future of adaptive learning in Nigeria? For special education schools

Mr A: I hope that in the future adaptive learning tools will be more available and tailored to our students' specific needs,...

Mr A: not just copied from education models.

Interviewer: Okay.

Interviewer: Thank you so very much. Once again, I really appreciate you for honoring my invite to this meeting. That will be all for today.

Interviewer: Do have a lovely and wonderful evening. You can leave the call, sir. Thank you so much.

Mr A: Yeah. Yeah. Welcome.

Interview 2

Interviewer: Hi. Good afternoon, sir. Hannah, how are you doing? I'm fine as well. Before we move on to this thing for today, thank you so much for accepting my invites for the meeting.

Mr B: Yeah. Yeah. Welcome. ...

Interviewer: All right. So, without wasting much of our time, let's move on to the question. so the first question goes sir what are the most common types of learning disabilities you encounter among students in your school

Mr B: To my own knowledge, what I would say is I've noticed that a good number of our students have attention deficit issues. Some can't stay focused for more than a few minutes at a time.

Mr B: Yeah. I also noticed that many of them struggle to remember...

Interviewer: Okay, the next question.

Interviewer: What specific learning challenges do students with learning disabilities face on a daily basis? Okay.

Mr B: what they were taught the previous days. which makes retention a big issue.

Interviewer: Next question. How do these challenges affect this student's academic progress and their overall development?

Mr B: I would say personally I notice that some students lose interest in learning altogether. The constant struggle makes them feel like they can't succeed.

Interviewer: I see.

Interviewer: I see. All right. So, the next question.

Mr B: Personally, I have a lot of visual aids like charts.

Interviewer: What teaching strategies have you found the most effective in supporting students with learning disabilities?

Mr B: It makes learning more for them.

Interviewer: Okay. I'm sorry sir I can't hear...

Interviewer: what you said very well the other time to situations in connection. What do you say? Okay. Yes. Yes. Yes..

Mr B: I said okay I said personally can you hear me personally a lot of visual aids like charts drawings and...

Mr B: real life objects it makes learning more concrete for Yeah.

Interviewer: Thank you so much. How accessible are technological tools for learning in your school?

Mr B: Personally, I've never used any digital tools in class because we don't have electricity most of the time, let alone devices. And I've tried to use a projector before,...

Interviewer: Okay, moving on.

Interviewer: Sir, what kind of infrastructural barriers have you possibly encountered whenever you're trying to use educational technology in your classroom? Okay. ...

Mr B: but the classroom has no sockets or stable surfaces to set it up properly. Yeah. ...

Interviewer: Thank you so much for that reply. Moving on to the next question. How familiar are you with adaptive learning systems and how they function?

Mr B: Personally, I've read a little about them online. I understand they are just content based on the student learning piece but I haven't seen one in use.

Interviewer: Okay, the next question without wasting much of our time.

Interviewer: Sir, how do you tailor your teaching methods to suit students with varying learning needs?

Mr B: Personally I adjust the pace of my lessons depending on the group.

Interviewer: Okay. ...

Mr B: Some students have more time so I slow down and give them extra practice.

Interviewer: The next question, How involved are caregivers or parents in supporting the use of adaptive learning technologies at home or in the school?

Mr B: And I have spoken to some caregivers who are willing to support but they don't have access to smartphones or internet connectivity at home.

Interviewer: Okay.

Interviewer: Moving on. sir, what policy or government support is in place to help schools like yours, okay, implement adaptive learning technologies?

Mr B: Personally I have heard of government programs for ICT in education but they haven't reached us yet especially in special educational settings. I can hear your question, please.

Interviewer: All right.

Interviewer: The next question, sir. What are your expectations for the future of adaptive learning in Nigerian special educational schools? ...

Mr B: Perfect. Personally,...

Interviewer: I'll come again. What are your expectations for the future of adaptive learning in Nigerian special education schools?

Mr B: I expect the government to begin taking special education more seriously by investing in technology that truly supports individual learning differences.

Interviewer: All So, that will be the last question for today. Thank you so much for your time and I really appreciate.

Mr B: Yeah. You're welcome.

Interviewer: So, you can leave the call now.

Mr B: Okay.

Interview 3

Interviewer: Hi. Good afternoon. How are you doing, sir?

Mr C: Yeah, I'm good. Yeah. You're welcome.

Interviewer: fine as All right. So, before we proceed, I would like to appreciate you and thank you so much for accepting my invite to join this meeting. I really appreciate. All right. moving on. The first question sir, are you hearing me?

Mr C: Yeah. Yeah. Yeah. Personally, I work with many children...

Interviewer: So sir, what are the most common types of learning disabilities you have encountered among students in your school?

Mr C: who have speech and language disorders. They struggle to express themselves or understand instructions. I see student getting frustrated.

Interviewer: All right.

Interviewer: Thank you so much for that reply. moving on, the next question. What specific learning challenges do students with learning disabilities face on a daily basis? All right.

Mr C: dead because they can't keep up with their case. It affects their confidence and willingness to participate.

Interviewer: Sir, how do these learning challenges affect students' academic progress and...

Interviewer: their overall development?

Mr C: And these challenges often make them repeat classes or lag behind. And over time it creates a sense of failure and frustration in them.

Interviewer: Okay sir.

Interviewer: Thank you so much for that reply.

Interviewer: Sir, what teaching strategies have you found the most effective to support students with learning disabilities?

Mr C: Come here,...

Mr C: please. repetition really works.

Interviewer: I mean sir, what teaching strategies have you found most effective?

Interviewer: Okay.

Mr C: Can you hear me now?

Mr C: Can you hear me?

Interviewer: Yes, I can hear you.

Mr C: I said repetition really works.

Interviewer: Yes, I can.

Mr C: Repetition really works. I have to go over a topic multiple times using different methods.

Interviewer: Okay. ...

Mr C: before most of my students grab it.

Interviewer: Thank you so much for that reply. the next question, sir. How accessible are technological tools for learning in your school?

Mr C: And we have a few donated laptops,...

Mr C: but they are outdated and shared among many teachers. So we really use them with students.

Interviewer: All right.

Interviewer: Moving on. What infrastructural barriers have you encountered whenever you try to use educational technology in your classroom?

Mr C: In my school we don't have a computer lab or...

Mr C: even a single working computer for students that limits everything. I've never used any adaptive learning tools in my classroom,...

Interviewer: All right.

Interviewer: Moving on. How familiar are you with adaptive learning systems and how they function?

Mr C: but I think they could really help,...

Mr C: especially the students who learn at different speeds. Students will learn at different speeds.

Interviewer: has different water.

Interviewer: Okay. All right. the next one. How do you tailor your teaching methods to suit students with varying learning needs? Okay.

Mr C: Yeah, I often divide my students into smaller groups based on their ability levels and give them different tasks that match their strength.

Interviewer: All right.

Mr C: Okay, come.

Interviewer: How involved are caregivers or parents in supporting the use of adaptive learning technologies at home or in school?

Mr C: Many of the parents I interact with are not literate. So using any form of learning technology is completely unfamiliar to them. There was a training session organized by the education board 2 years ago...

Interviewer: What policy or government exists to help schools like yours implement adaptive learning technologies?

Mr C: but it was not specifically for adaptive technology. It was more generally digital literacy. Yeah. I am hopeful that with more awareness,...

Interviewer: Okay.

Interviewer: The last question for today sir, what are your expectations for the future of adaptive learning in Nigerian special education schools? Okay.

Mr C: schools will finally get the resources and training needed to use adaptive systems effectively. You're welcome.

Interviewer: Okay, sir. Thank you so much for every one of your responses and feedback. I really appreciate. So, that concludes the interview for today.

Interviewer: You can actually end the meeting. Yeah.

Mr C: Okay.

Interview 4

Interviewer: Hi, good evening and how are you doing? Before we move on or proceed for what we are to do today, I would like to appreciate you and thank you for accepting Naiva to join the meeting. Thank you so much sir.

Mr D: I'm good.

Mr D: You are welcome. Yeah. Most of the learning challenges I see are related to intellectual disabilities.

Interviewer: All right. So the first question without wasting much of our time. What are the most common types of learning disabilities you have encountered among students in your school?

Mr D: Some students process information much slower than one of the biggest challenges is communication.

Interviewer: Okay, the next question. What specific learning challenges do students with learning disabilities face on a daily basis?

Mr D: Some of my students can't express themselves clearly. So they often keep quiet when they are confused. I've observed that some students withdraw socially.

Interviewer: Moving on to the third question. Sir, how do these learning challenges affect students' academic progress and their overall development?

Mr D: They feel different or...

Interviewer: Mhm. ...

Mr D: ashamed especially when other students make fun of them. I often use storytelling and...

Interviewer: The next question. What teaching strategies have you found most effective whenever you support students that have learning disabilities? Thank you so much for that response.

Mr D: role playing because many of them respond well to activities that involve movement and imagination. The internet is a major issue.

Interviewer: The next question, how accessible are technological tools for learning in your school?

Interviewer: Okay.

Mr D: Even if we add devices, there's no reliable connection to support online learning or research. I would say internet assets is a huge barrier.

Interviewer: The next question. What infrastructural barriers have you probably encountered whenever you try to use educational technology in your classroom when teaching the students?

Mr D: Without data or reliable network it's impossible to stream educational content or...

Interviewer: Okay.

Mr D: use online tools.

Interviewer: So, okay, that's good. Thank you so much, the next question,...

Interviewer: sir, how familiar have you been with adaptive learning systems and do you know how they function?

Mr D: Yeah, sure.

Mr D: I know a bit about it from a workshop I attended. The idea is to tailor the learning experience to each student's idea for special education.

Interviewer: All Okay. How do you tailor your teaching methods to suit students that,...

Interviewer: learns that their learning needs vary?

Mr D: For students who struggle with writing, I allow oral responses or use drawing as an alternative way to express what they have learned.

Interviewer: Okay, next one.

Interviewer: How involved are caregivers or parents in supporting the use of adaptive learning technologies at home or in school settings?

Mr D: I've seen a few parents show interest, especially when we explain how it could help their child learn better, but they but they still rely on the school to handle everything.

Interviewer: Okay, moving on to the next one.

Interviewer: What policy or government exists to help students like yours to help them implement adaptive learning technologies?

Mr D: Okay, I will say in my experience the policies are there on paper but implementation is a real problem. We don't get the equipment or followup needed effectively. Okay.

Interviewer: Okay.

Interviewer: So, this is the last question I'll be asking you now.

Interviewer: What are your expectations for the future of adaptive learning in Nigerian special education schools?

Mr D: My expectations right?

Interviewer: Yeah. Yeah. Your expectations.

Mr D: I expect that technology will help us close the learning gap for students with disabilities if the tools are affordable and inclusive. Yeah.

Interviewer: All Thank you for the feedback.

Mr D: Thank you.

Interviewer: I really appreciate.

Interviewer: So, that'll be all. do have a lovely day ahead. You can end the call. Yeah. Yeah. Thank you.

Mr D: Welcome. Okay.

Interview 5

Interviewer: Hi, how are you doing? All right. Okay. So, before we proceed into what we have for today, I'd like to thank you for accepting my invite to join this meeting. Thank you so much, sir. I really appreciate.

Mr E: I'm good.

Mr E: Okay. You're welcome.

Interviewer: All without further ado, I will ask the first question. What are the most common types of learning disabilities you probably encounter among students in your school?

Interviewer:

Mr E: I encounter students with andalia often.

Mr E: They have serious difficulty with basic ones like counting, addition or reorganizing numbers.

Interviewer: Okay.

Interviewer: Moving on to the next question. Sir, what specific learning challenges do students with learning disabilities face on a daily basis?

Mr E: I have students who can't sit still or focus for more than a few minutes. It is difficult to maintain their attention during lessons.

Interviewer: Okay.

Interviewer: Moving on to the next question. How does these learning challenges,...

Interviewer: how do they affect students' academic progress and their overall development? All right,...

Mr E: Their communication difficulties make it hard for them to ask questions or seek help. This limits their growth not just academically but also socially.

Interviewer: thanks for that response.

Interviewer: What teaching strategies have you found most effective in supporting students with learning disabilities? Yeah. ...

Mr E: For me, individualized instruction is key. I try to give each student a task suited to their ability level.

Mr E: So they don't feel empty.

Interviewer: So, how accessible are technological tools for learning in your school? Okay.

Mr E: I've tried using my phone to show educational videos, but it is not sustainable, especially with large classes and not reject them. Our classrooms are overcrowded and...

Interviewer: The next question, sir. What infrastructural barriers have you encountered whenever you try to use educational technology in your classroom? All right.

Mr E: ntilated. There is no space to safely use or store devices like laptops and speakers.

Interviewer: How familiar are you with adaptive learning systems and how they function?

Mr E: Yeah. Can you hear me?

Interviewer: Yes, I can. Did you hear what I said?

Mr E: Yeah, I can hear you.

Interviewer: Did you hear what I said?

Mr E: Yes. Yes.

Interviewer: Should I repeat the question again?

Mr E: Yeah, repeat the question.

Interviewer: Okay I asked that how familiar are you with adaptive learning systems and how they function? Okay, the next one.

Mr E: In my experience, we have not had access to any kind of systems based on observation and experience.

Interviewer: How do you tailor your teaching methods to suit students with varying learning needs? All right.

Mr E: What I use is repetition,...

Mr E: a lot of repetition and checking with students individually to make sure they understand before moving on. what I would say is most of them don't see the importance most of them don't see the importance...

Interviewer: The next question. How involved are caregivers or parents to support the use of adaptive learning technologies at home or in the school?

Mr E: because they have not been exposed to adaptive learning tools themselves so there's a lack of

Mr E: I'll be honest. Yeah, I know some private organizations that have partnered with the government to provide laptops or...

Interviewer: The next question sir,...

Interviewer: What policy or government support actually exists to aid students like yours implement adaptive learning technologies? All right.

Mr E: projectors to selected schools, but we have not benefited

Mr E: It's in the future.

Interviewer: Which is the last question for today. What are your expectations for the future of adaptive learning in Nigerian special education schools?

Mr E: I want to see every special education classroom equipped with at least basic adaptive software and trained staff to use it properly.

Interviewer: Okay, so that'll be all for the interview for today.

Interviewer: Thank you so much for your time. I really appreciate. Do have a nice day.

Mr E: You're welcome.

Interviewer: So that will be all for today. You can end the call.

Interview 6

Interviewer: Hi, how are you doing today?

Mr F: I'm good.

Mr F: And you

Interviewer: I'm good as Thank you so much for honoring to join the meeting today for the questions I'll be asking you.

Interviewer: Thank you so much. I really appreciate.

Mr F: Can you come again please?

Interviewer: So without wasting much of our time, I'll begin by asking the questions now. sir, what are the most common types of learning disabilities you encounter among students in your school?

Interviewer: I Okay,...

Interviewer: I asked you what are the most common types of learning disabilities you encounter among students in your school?

Mr F: In my experience, some students have multiple disabilities like hearing loss combined with cognitive delays which makes teaching more complex.

Interviewer: M okay the next question thanks for that reply anyways the next question sir...

Interviewer: what specific learning challenges do students that have learning disabilities face on a daily basis

Mr F: I'm going to say handwriting is a problem for some of them.

Mr F: They find it hard to form letters correctly or copy notes from the board.

Interviewer: Okay.

Interviewer: So, how do these learning challenges affect students' academic progress and their overall development?

Mr F: And from my experience, poor performance affects their motivation. They stop participating in class activities and sometimes avoid committing over time...

Interviewer: All Moving on to the next question. From your experience, what teaching strategies have you found the most effective whenever you support students with learning disabilities?

Mr F: What I've used is I mix audio visuals and hands-on activities in my lessons. That small sensory approach helps students with different learning styles stay engaged.

Interviewer: Okay. ...

Interviewer: how accessible are technological tools for learning in your school? Okay.

Mr F: Technology is not really accessible here. Many students have never even touched a computer. So digital learning is almost impossible.

Interviewer: What infrastructural barriers have you encountered in trying to use educational technology in your classroom.

Mr F: I have had cases where I wanted to use materials but due to the noise from nearby roads the student could not hear anything clearly. I've come across some apps that suggest...

Interviewer: How familiar are you with adaptive learning systems and how they function?

Mr F: What to teach next based on how the student performed on the quiz. I think that is an example of an adaptive learning system.

Interviewer: Okay, thanks for the reply. The next question, how do you tailor your teaching method to suit students with varying learning needs?

Mr F: Yeah, in my class I mixed the whole class teaching with oneonone. Some students just need that extra attention to stay on track.

Interviewer: Yeah, that's a very good method. Moving on, how involved are caregivers or parents in supporting the use of adaptive learning technologies at home or...

Interviewer: in school?

Mr F: I've had a few caregivers who are supportive, but they expect the school to provide everything. They can't afford devices or data at home.

Interviewer: Okay.

Interviewer: The next question.

Interviewer: What policy or government support is in place to help schools like yours implement adaptive learning technologies?

Mr F: Now to be honest, I don't think there is much awareness among government officials about the needs of special education schools or learners with disabilities. Hello, can you hear me?

Interviewer: Yes, I can hear you.

Mr F: I don't think there is much awareness among government officials about the needs of special education schools when it comes to adaptive learning.

Interviewer: Okay, thank you so much. All right. the last question that we'll be asking you for today, what are your expectations for the future of adaptive learning in Nigerian special education schools?

Mr F: My expectation is that parents and caregivers will also be trained so that learning does not stop at school. Adaptive learning should continue at home too.

Interviewer: Okay.

Interviewer: So that'll be all for today. Thank you so much for your time. Really Do have a link today and you can end the call. I'll be on.

Mr F: You're welcome.

Interview 7

Interviewer: Hello,...

Interviewer: Good evening and how are you doing?

Mrs G: I'm very fine.

Mrs G: Good evening.

Interviewer: So before we proceed on what we have for today, I would like to thank you for accepting my invite to join the meeting for today. Thank you so much.

Mrs G: You're welcome.

Interviewer: All right, without wasting much of our time, I'll begin by asking the first question. And if you don't...

Interviewer: If you can't hear me properly, you can just signify by telling me. All the first question, what are the most common types of learning disabilities you encounter among students in your school?

Mrs G: Look at me.

Mrs G: I see quite a few students with autism spectrum disorder.

Mrs G: They tend to have challenges with social interaction and communication which affect their learning too. Thank you.

Interviewer: All right.

Interviewer: The next question. What specific learning challenges do students with learning disabilities face on a daily basis?

Mrs G: For some reading and writing are extremely slow processes. They get tired easily and sometimes give up halfway through a task.

Interviewer: All right.

Interviewer: All right. Thanks for that response. the next question. Ma'am, how do these learning challenges affect students' academic progress and their overall development?

Mrs G: I have worked with students...

Mrs G: who are very intelligent but can't express their thoughts because of language difficulties. This affect...

Interviewer: Okay. ...

Mrs G: how they are perceived and how they see themselves.

Interviewer: That's a very nice answer. Moving on to the next question. What teaching strategies have you found the most effective over the years whenever you support students with learning disabilities?

Mrs G: Positive reinforcement actually goes a long way.

Mrs G: I always not just to correct answers...

Interviewer: Okay. ...

Mrs G: but to build their confidence.

Interviewer: moving on to the next question. How accessible are technological tools for learning in your school?

Mrs G: I believe tech could help but most of us have not been trained on how to use it effectively in teaching, especially for students with disabilities.

Interviewer:

Interviewer: What infrastructural barriers have you encountered whenever you try to use educational technology in your classroom to teach students?

Mrs G: Even when I bring my phone to class for educational purposes, I can't charge it in school and there's no backup power.

Interviewer: Okay.

Interviewer: Moving on to the next question. How familiar are you with adaptive learning systems and how they function?

Mrs G: To be honest, I'm not sure how they function technically, but if they can adjust to individual learning challenges, that will be very useful for our school. Thank you.

Interviewer: Okay, thank you as well.

Mrs G: You're welcome.

Interviewer: How do you tailor your teaching methods to suit students with varying learning needs?

Mrs G: I always prepare extra learning materials such as flashcards and simplified notes for students who need more effort.

Interviewer: how involved are caregivers or parents in supporting the use of adaptive learning technologies at home or in the school?

Mrs G: Personally, I think the willingness is there, but the capacity is lacking. Many families are just trying to survive and don't prioritize learning tools.

Interviewer: Okay.

Interviewer: So, what policy or government support is in place to help schools like yours implement these adaptive learning technologies?

Mrs G: I've heard of NITA and other agencies supporting digital education, but nothing has been done specifically for our school or learners with disabilities.

Interviewer: So the last question for today,...

Mrs G: Personally,...

Interviewer: What are your expectations for the future?

Interviewer: What do you expect for the future of adaptive learning in Nigerian special education schools?

Mrs G: I believe adaptive learning has great potential, but only if rural and special schools are not left behind in national digital education plans.

Interviewer: Okay. Thank you so very much, Ma. That will be the last question of today.

Mrs G: I need to All Okay.

Interviewer: Have a lovely day and thank you so much. So, you can leave the call Ma.

Interview 8

Interviewer: Hello, good evening and...

Interviewer: How are you doing today?

Mrs H: I'm very fine and you?

Mrs H: Okay. You're welcome. Okay.

Interviewer: So before we proceed,...

Interviewer: I would like to appreciate you for actually taking part of your time to accept my invite for this meeting. I really appreciate this meeting and this is mainly for the purpose of my research of which I'm conducting. So your personal information won't be disclosed. So without wasting much of our time let's move on to the questions for today.

Interviewer: So the first question goes...

Interviewer: what are the most common types of learning disabilities you encounter among students in your school.

Mrs H: Yes, quite a number of our learners show signs of visual processing disorders.

Mrs H: They mix up letters or struggle with reading from the board.

Interviewer: Okay, the next question.

Interviewer: So what specific learning challenges do students with learning disabilities face on a daily basis?

Mrs H: I have seen how peer pressure affects them. When others laugh at their mistakes, they withdraw and stop trying.

Interviewer: Okay, that's a good one.

Interviewer: The next question, how do these learning challenges affect students' academic progress and their overall development?

Mrs H: These learning difficulties also affect their ability to develop life skills. Some can't follow basic routines or instructions which affect their independence.

Interviewer: All right. Thanks for the feedback.

Mrs H: You're welcome.

Interviewer: What teaching strategies have you found the most effective in supporting students with learning disabilities? Okay.

Mrs H: I have also seen improvement when I use peer learning. Pairing stronger students with those who would need help encourages social and academic growth.

Interviewer: So, how accessible are the technical technological tools for learning in your school?

Mrs H: Sometimes I download audio materials at home and play them in class using a small speaker. That's the most we can do for now.

Interviewer: The next question. Can you state any infrastructural barriers that you have encountered whenever you try to use educational technology in your classroom?

Mrs H: Personally, I find it difficult to plan tech based lessons because we never know when we will have power or if the device will actually work.

Interviewer: Okay, the next question.

Interviewer: How familiar are you with adaptive learning systems and...

Interviewer: Do you know how they function?

Mrs H: Okay. Though I've never used one, but I'm very interested. I think if teachers in rural or special schools are trained properly, we can benefit a lot from such systems.

Interviewer: All right. moving on to the next question. How do you tailor your teaching materials to actually suit students that their learning needs vary?

Mrs H: Personally, I also involve peer tutoring. Some of the more advanced students help explain things to their classmates in a way they understand.

Interviewer: All right.

Interviewer: How involved are caregivers or parents in supporting the use of adaptive learning technologies at home or in the school.

Mrs H: Some parents are actually afraid of technology and think it might confuse or harm their child, especially those with learning disabilities.

Interviewer: So from your experience, do you know of any policy or...

Interviewer: if there's a government support system in place to help schools like yours implement adaptive learning technologies?

Mrs H: In my school, we rely more on NGO support than the government. The policies sound good, but there's a huge gap in terms of actual delivery.

Interviewer: Okay.

Interviewer: The last question for today ...

Interviewer: What are your expectations for the future of adaptive learning in Nigerian special education schools?

Mrs H: I expect more partnership between the government and private tech companies to develop local context appropriate solutions for our students.

Interviewer: Okay, once again, thank you so much for your time with me. I really appreciate.

Mrs H: You're welcome.

Interviewer: So, this concludes the meeting for today.

Mrs H: All right.

Interviewer: Do have a wonderful day ahead.

Mrs H: Thank you.

Interview 9

Interviewer: Hello. How are you doing?

Mr I: I'm good. You're welcome.

Interviewer: I'm fine as thank you for accepting my invite to join the meeting for today. All right, so without further ado, let's move on to the first question. T what are the most common types of learning disabilities you encounter among students in your school?

Mr I: I'm going to say from what I've seen, I have students who experience nonverbal learning disabilities. They do okay with reading but struggle with understanding special relationships or social cues. I would say one of the challenges they face is that most of them need individualized attention...

Interviewer: Okay, the next question.

Interviewer: What specific learning challenges the students with learning disabilities face on a daily basis? Okay. All right.

Mr I: but with limited staff it has to give them that support consistency. That's what I've experienced on a daily basis. Most of them need individualized attention, but with limited staff, it's hard to give them that support consistently.

Interviewer: Thanks for that. Moving on to the next question.

Interviewer: How do these learning challenges affect students' academic progress and their overall development?

Mr I: I find that emotional development is also delayed.

Mr I: Many of them deal with anxiety or low self-confidence because of their academic struggles.

Interviewer: The next question,...

Interviewer: what teaching strategies have you found the most effective in supporting students with any learning disabilities?

Mr I: Personally, I create a predictable routine in class.

Mr I: Many of my students feel more what would I say?

Mr I: They feel more secure and focused when they know what to expect. We were promised digital...

Interviewer: Okay, that's good.

Interviewer: How accessible are technological tools for learning in your school?

Mr I: and learning tools but they never arrived. So we still rely on posters, flashcards and manual teaching aids.

Interviewer: Okay.

Interviewer: What infrastructural barriers have you probably encountered in trying to use educational technology in your classroom?

Mr I: Our walls are peeling and roofs leak and dust gets everywhere. These conditions make it risky to bring in any technology without damaging it.

Interviewer: All right.

Interviewer: Moving on to the next question. How familiar are you with adaptive learning systems and how they function?

Mr I: I'm somewhat familiar with the concept.

Mr I: It's like using data to personalize learning, right? But we haven't had the resources to explore it further.

Interviewer: Okay.

Interviewer: How do you tailor your teaching methods to suit students that their learning needs vary a lot?

Mr I: I try to observe each student closely and adjust my instructions to suit their preferred learning style. Some like listening while others prefer doing In my school,...

Interviewer: So how involved are caregivers or parents in supporting the use of adaptive learning technologies at home or in school?

Mr I: We've tried involving parents through meetings and training sessions, but turnout is usually low unless there is a financial incentive.

Interviewer: U...

Mr I: Personally, I feel that...

Interviewer: what policy or government exist to help schools value of training implement adaptive learning technologies.

Mr I: if there was more followup from the Ministry of Education or local education authorities, we would have seen more progress in using adaptive technology.

Interviewer: This is the last question for today.

Interviewer: What are your expectations for the future of adaptive learning in Nigeria special education schools?

Mr I: What I would say is I'm optimistic. But I also think it takes strong policy enforcement and: constant monitoring to make adaptive learning a reality in special schools.

Interviewer: That is going to be all for today. Thank you so much for your time. I really appreciate. Okay, so that will be all. You can leave the class with Drew.

Interview 10

Interviewer: The first question, what are the most common types of learning disabilities you encounter among students in your school?

Mr J: From what I've seen, slow learning is very common. This student needs a lot more time and repetition to understand even basic concepts.

Interviewer: The next one,...

Interviewer: What specific learning challenges do students with learning disabilities face on a daily basis?

Mr J: Many of them have difficulty following step-by-step instructions especially in subjects like mathematics or science practicals.

Interviewer: How do these learning challenges affect students' academic progress and their overall development?

Mr J: Yes, the impact goes beyond academics. It affects their relationships with peers, their behavior in class, and even their readiness for life after school.

Interviewer: Okay, I get that a lot now.

Interviewer: What learning strategies have you found the most effective in your teaching experience whenever you're trying to support students with learning disabilities?

Mr J: Often I use frequent assessments not to grade them but to know where they are struggling and adjust my teaching accordingly.

Interviewer: How accessible are technological tools for learning in your school?

Mr J: In my own view I think the idea of using technology is great but until the government invests in basic infrastructure it remains out of reach for schools like mine.

Interviewer: What infrastructural barriers have you encountered in trying to use educational technology in your classroom?

Mr J: We don't have technical support. If a device stops working, there is no one to fix it.

Mr J: So many of us have just stopped trying to use tech at all.

Interviewer: the next question, how familiar are you with adaptive learning systems and...

Interviewer: how do they function?

Mr J: No, I'm not that familiar with adaptive learning systems, but I would love to learn Anything that can help me teach more effectively is welcome.

Interviewer: Okay. Next question. How do you tailor your teaching methods to suit students with varying learning needs?

Mr J: What I do is that I make my classroom flexible. Some students learn better standing or moving around. So I don't force everyone to sit still all the time.

Interviewer: Okay, thanks for the reply. The next question, how involved are caregivers or parents in supporting the use of adaptive learning technologies at home or in school?

Mr J: I think if we add a way to show caregivers simple practical ways to use these tools maybe in their local language they will be more involved but as of now they are involved there is no real support right now that yeah can you hear me also I said for now there is no real support we have written letters proposals...

Interviewer: Okay. Okay.

Interviewer: What policy or government support is in place to help schools like yours implement adaptive learning technologies? Hello, sir. Can you hear me? Yeah, I can. Okay. Okay.

Mr J: but nothing has been done to help us implement anything adaptively ...

Interviewer: All right. the last question for today, what are your expectations for the future of adaptive learning in Nigerian special education schools?

Mr J: I hope to see a future where students with learning disabilities can learn at their own pace without being made to feel different or left out.

Interviewer: Okay, thank you so much for your time. That will be all for today.

Interviewer: You can leave the call.

Appendix Three

Interview Questions

- i. What are the most common types of learning disabilities you encounter among students in your school?
- ii. What specific learning challenges do students with learning disabilities face on a daily basis?
How do these learning challenges affect students' academic progress and overall development?
- iii. What teaching strategies have you found most effective in supporting students with learning disabilities?
- iv. How accessible are technological tools for learning in your school?
- v. What infrastructural barriers have you encountered in trying to use educational technology in your classroom?
- vi. How familiar are you with adaptive learning systems and how they function?
- vii. How do you tailor your teaching methods to suit students with varying learning needs?
- viii. How involved are caregivers or parents in supporting the use of adaptive learning technologies at home or in school?
- ix. What policy or government support exists to help schools like yours implement adaptive learning technologies?
- x. What are your expectations for the future of adaptive learning in Nigerian special education schools?